

CRITICAL PERFORMANCE ROLES OF SCHOOL HEADS AND CITY SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF CABUYAO

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Critical Performance Roles of School Heads and City Schools in the Division of Cabuyao

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the level of manifestation of critical performance roles among school heads and the level of school performance in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao that becomes the basis in crafting the performance roles mentoring program. As the results revealed, the level of manifestation of critical performance roles of school heads in terms of relational, authentic, visionary, quality and service leadership were all highly manifested. There is no significant difference between the assessments of teachers and school heads on the critical performance roles. In terms of school achievement rate, none of the public schools has gotten a high level of school achievement rate. In terms of Teachers' Performance, there have been 14% of the teachers who have outstanding level of performance. Meanwhile, 86% of the teachers' performances fall in the very satisfactory level of performance. It implies that there is significant relationship between the level of manifestation of critical performance roles among school heads and school performance in terms of service and teachers' performance. On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the level of manifestation of critical performance roles among school heads and school performance in relational, authentic, visionary and quality leadership. Based from the findings, the school heads are able to establish good relationship with their teachers and stakeholders; able to perform their duties particularly in developing and promoting an open and change-friendly culture; able to demonstrate leadership skill which focuses in producing self-directed and quality learners by creating and implementing school programs and projects; able to exhibit excellent leadership in handling the teachers, dealing with the school stakeholders, and managing school operations. It also depicts that the teachers' performance in school has been influenced by the service leadership of their school heads. It also hints that teachers are capacitated by the school principals in doing priority assessment needs of the school that increase their school performance.

Keywords: *performance, critical, manifestation, schools, leadership*

Introduction

Educational leadership is a collaborate process that unites the talents and forces of teachers, students and parents. The goal of educational leadership is to improve the quality of education and the education system itself.

As it is, quality education is the need of modern societies. The capacity of an educational enterprise to provide the relevant learning experiences for learners in the dynamic and ever-changing world has driven schools to become responsive since the 21st century education demands for better preparation of learners in the basic education to be equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes. If learners in the basic education have strong foundation for learning, then when they get to higher education they will become innovative and competitive, and ultimately, they will become successful contributors to national development.

Currently, the thrust of the Department of Education to empower school heads and emphasize school-based management have increased and intensified. This major trend of practice in current education reform aims at improving the quality of education services by the government and schools both public and private as well.

With these compelling reasons and situations, the researcher has been motivated to conduct the study to give insights on the critical performance roles where school heads are expected to know, understand, and perform as leaders.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive correlational research was used for this study to test the relationship between the dependent variable and one or more independent variables. This design was appropriate for the study since this determined the level of manifestation of critical performance roles among school heads and its significant relationship to the level of school performance which was concerned with current condition or situations.

Quantitative methods emphasized objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. This design focused on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or to explain a particular phenomenon.

Respondents

This study used the simple random sampling to give all possible chances to all school heads and teachers to be included in the study. According to QuestionPro (n.d.), simple random sampling is a sampling technique where every item in the population has an even

chance and likelihood of being selected in the sample. Here the selection of items completely depends on chance or by probability and therefore this sampling technique is also sometimes known as a method of chances. A simple random sample is a fair sampling technique.

Simple random sampling is a very basic type of sampling method and can easily be a component of a more complex sampling method. The main attribute of this sampling method is that every sample has the same probability of being chosen.

The sample size in this sampling method should ideally be more than a few hundred so that simple random sampling can be applied in an appropriate manner. It is sometimes argued that this method is theoretically simple to understand but difficult to practically implement. Working with large sample size is not an easy task and it can sometimes be a challenge finding a realistic sampling frame.

This study covered school heads in all public schools and selected teachers in the City Schools Division of Cabuyao City, Laguna. The table that follows provides information on this.

Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire as instrument of the study. The first part included the respondents' information. The second part dealt with the level of manifestation of critical performance roles of school heads in terms of relational, authentic, visionary, quality, and service leadership. The researcher made a survey questionnaire guided by the model designed by William Spady entitled *The Critical Performance Roles: relational, authentic, visionary, quality, and service leaders*. For easy administration, scoring and assessment of the survey questionnaire, the Likert scale was utilized to easily obtain the responses. The four (4) point scale ranging from four (4) being the highest and one (1) as the lowest was used.

The first draft of the questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for comments and corrections. The suggestions of the panel members were also considered for the validation of the questionnaire. The questionnaire helped the researcher gather school heads' assessment on the level of manifestation of critical performance roles.

Procedure

A letter of request was sent to the City Schools Division of Cabuyao to allow the researcher to conduct the study in all public schools in Department of Education Cabuyao. Moreover, individual letters of request were given to the school heads of the public. This letter sought approval regarding the collection of assessments from school heads and their teachers. Afterwards, the researcher provided a set of questionnaires to the school heads who assessed themselves. The questionnaires were retrieved immediately and tabulated for analysis and interpretation of data.

Data Analysis

The following were the statistical treatment applied to the study using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

- Frequency and percentage were used to determine the frequency of occurrence of the level of manifestation of critical performance of school heads and the level of school performance.
- T-test for independent samples was used to determine the difference between the assessments of the school heads and teachers.
- The mean and the four-point Likert Scale were used to evaluate the level of manifestation of critical performance roles of school heads.
- Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to determine the relationship between the level of manifestation of critical performance roles of school heads and the level of school performance.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical concerns were followed by the researcher as those are taken into account throughout this paper. Consent was asked wherein confidentiality was assured. All the necessary details were explained by the researcher for them to understand their role upon the completion of the study. Information personal to the respondents was assured to have its confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

Based on the data gathered and after careful and thorough analysis of the investigation, the following are the findings of the study in summarized form.

Level of Manifestation of Critical Performance Roles among School Heads of City Division of Cabuyao City as Assessed by School Heads themselves and their Teachers

In terms of Relational Leadership, the general composite mean is 3.67 and is interpreted as Highly Manifested.

In terms of Authentic Leadership, it has a general composite mean of 3.73 and is interpreted as Highly Manifested.

In terms of Visionary Leadership, it has a general mean composite of 3.76 and is interpreted as Highly Manifested.

In terms of Quality Leadership, it has a general composite mean of 3.75 and is interpreted as Highly Manifested.

In terms of Service Leadership, it has a general composite mean of 3.73 and is interpreted as Highly Manifested.

Test of Significant Difference between the Assessments of the Two Groups of Respondents

There is no significant difference between the assessments of teachers and school heads on the critical performance roles of school heads.

Level of School Performance of Public Elementary Schools of the City Division of Cabuyao City

In terms of School Achievement Rate, 9 or 30% of the public schools in Cabuyao City have a low level of school achievement rate while 21 or 70% of the schools belong to the average level of school achievement rate.

In terms of Teachers' Performance, there are 14 or 14% of the teachers who have outstanding level of performance which ratings are from 90 to 100. Meanwhile, 86 teachers or 86% of the teachers' performance rating are from 85-89 and fall under the very satisfactory level of performance.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of Critical Performance Roles among School Heads of the City Division of Cabuyao and School Performance

There is significant relationship between the level of manifestation of critical performance roles among school heads in the City Division of Cabuyao and school performance in terms of service and teachers' performance as shown in the probability value of .03 which is less than the level of significance at .05.

On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the level of manifestation of critical performance roles among school heads of the City Division of Cabuyao and school performance in all other critical performance roles. The probability values are greater than the level of significance at .05.

The Proposed Mentoring Program

As an output of this study, a critical performance roles mentoring program is proposed to enhance principals' characteristics and attributes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions have been derived: School heads are effective in establishing good relationships with their teachers and stakeholders, fulfilling their duties by promoting an open and change-friendly culture. They assist teachers in identifying their strengths and growth areas while providing necessary technical support. School principals exemplify the department's core values and principles, inspiring teachers and stakeholders to generate positive changes within the school environment. They exhibit reliable leadership by treating teachers equally and ensuring that all organizational functions and decisions are aligned with the school's purpose and goals.

Moreover, school principals demonstrate leadership skills focused on fostering self-directed and quality learners. They achieve this by creating and implementing programs and projects that benefit the students, school, and community. Their leadership also extends to effectively managing teachers, engaging with stakeholders, and overseeing school operations. Additionally, it is evident that teachers and other stakeholders are empowered in planning and conducting school-related activities, projects, and programs. Principals also recognize and commend the efforts of their teaching and non-teaching staff, employing a positive reward system that motivates them to contribute towards achieving the organization's vision and mission.

The study further concludes that the level of critical performance roles of school heads is consistent across different groups of respondents. Regardless of group classification, teachers observed similar performance roles of their school heads. Although this finding indicates non-significance in terms of differences among groups, it does not detract from the guiding principles employed by school heads in their duties. Most public schools involved in the study share similar levels of school achievement rates, but educational management practices still vary. This underscores the need for the creation and implementation of effective curricular programs to enhance student academic performance and strengthen foundational approaches, strategies, and innovative activities.

Furthermore, the study reveals that a significant number of teacher-respondents have not yet achieved the highest performance level, as many are still working towards attaining the "Outstanding" bracket of 90-100. This suggests there is ample opportunity for improvement and encouragement to enhance teacher performance. It is also noted that teachers' performance in school is influenced by the service leadership of their school heads, who encourage good work and incorporate a positive reward system to motivate staff to work towards the school's vision and mission. School heads play a crucial role in capacitating teachers through priority assessment needs, which in turn improves overall school performance. Finally, the study suggests that a proposed critical performance roles mentoring program is necessary to further enhance the characteristics and attributes of school principals.

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